

COMPARATIVE LEGAL ANALYSIS OF THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THE RIGHT OF INVIOABILITY OF HOME IN THE CONSTITUTIONAL NORMS OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11273764>

When conducting a comparative analysis of the constitutions of different countries and dividing them into three groups, the researcher took into account the specific application of the above terms. Based on the term used, we can see from what angle the emphasis was placed on the concept of inviolability of the home, including the concept of home itself.

According to Article 32 of the Estonian Constitution, the home is inviolable. No one may be subjected to forcible entry or search into a home, real or movable property under his control, or place of work, except in cases and in the manner prescribed by law, in order to protect public order, health or the rights and freedoms of others persons , to fight a criminal offense, to apprehend a criminal or to establish the truth in a criminal trial. As we see, according to the Constitution of Estonia, the right to inviolability of the home extends not only to the house where a person lives, but also to the place of work. It should be noted that they recognize both real and immovable property as a type of property as a dwelling.

Article 32 of the Constitution of Armenia also deals with the inviolability of the home, which states that everyone has the right to the inviolability of the home. In addition, the constitution itself prescribes for what purposes the inviolability of the home may be limited. For example, for the purpose of protecting national security, the economic well-being of the country, preventing or solving crimes, protecting public order, health and morals, or fundamental rights and freedoms. others. A search of a home can only be carried out by a court decision in cases and in the manner provided for by the law of Armenia. The law may provide for other cases of restriction of the right to inviolability of home by court decision.

Article 15 of the Belgian Constitution also provides for the inviolability of the home and refers to Belgian legislation.

If we study Article 5 of the Brazilian Constitution, the house is the inviolable refuge of a person, and no one can enter it without the consent of the occupant, except in the case of a crime scene, disaster or rescue, or during the daytime by order of the court. Analyzing the prescription of the Brazilian Constitution, as a unique feature, we noticed that the subject whose permission must be obtained to enter the house is indicated. But it is not defined what we should understand by the concept of home (dwelling).

The Greek Constitution, namely Article 9, states that every person's home is a sanctuary. No house search may be carried out except in cases prescribed by law and always in the presence of representatives of the judiciary. The Greek approach to ensuring and guaranteeing the inviolability of the home is unique in that, in addition to the legal approach, one can also see a philosophical approach, which says that the house is a sanctuary. Here the importance and high level of attitude towards the inviolability of the home is determined. In addition, the direct presence of representatives of the judiciary is always required to carry out any actions aimed at limiting the inviolability of the home.

The Constitution of the People's Republic of China states in Article 39 that the home of citizens of the People's Republic of China is inviolable. Unlawful search or entry into a citizen's home is prohibited. In previous constitutions of countries such as Estonia, Armenia, Belgium, Greece, we could see the range of subjects to whom the inviolability of the home applies. Due to the fact that the inviolability of the home relates to personal human rights, the persons to whom it applies were indicated as everyone. Only the Brazilian Constitution used the term tenant. And in the Constitution of the People's Republic of China, as a subject of legal relations, it is written that the home of citizens of the People's Republic of China is inviolable, which is a unique feature.

Part 1 of Article 10 of the Finnish Constitution states that everyone's privacy, honor and inviolability of home are guaranteed. The same article, in part 3, establishes that the law may establish measures that infringe on the inviolability of the home and are necessary to ensure fundamental rights and freedoms or to investigate crimes.

The Egyptian Constitution, namely Article 13, stipulates that houses are inviolable. Except in cases of danger or call for assistance, they may not be entered, searched, monitored, or wiretapped except by a judicial warrant specifying the place, time, and purpose. All of the above is carried out in cases provided for by law and in the prescribed manner. When entering or searching a house, those inside must be notified and informed of the warrant issued in this

regard. We again see a separate approach to understanding the inviolability of the home, which, in addition to entering and searching the house, also includes listening to conversations.

In the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Germany, in Article 13, Part 1, it is written that the home is inviolable and subsequent articles describe in what cases the rights of inviolability, order and procedure can be limited. And Article 8 of the Constitution of Great Britain states that everyone has the right to respect for their private and family life, home and correspondence.

In the comparative analysis of the constitutions of various countries in the context of the inviolability of the home, namely where the term home was used. In the context of the considered constitutions, the term “dwelling” is interpreted with some variations. This concept covers not only the physical space where a person lives, but can also include a place of work (as is the case with the Estonian Constitution). Also highlighted is the use of the term “home” (in the Brazilian and German Constitutions), which, in addition to simply indicating physical space, takes on additional aspects of refuge and privacy.

An interesting factor is the use of a philosophical approach in the Greek Constitution, where the house is described as a sanctuary, which emphasizes the high value and respect for the intimate area of citizens. While the Chinese Constitution emphasizes the inviolability of the citizens' home, without specifying its exact interpretation.

Restrictions on the privacy of the home also appear in constitutional texts, with the main reasons ranging from the protection of public order and security to the prevention of crime and the protection of the rights and freedoms of others.

Thus, the variety of interpretations and approaches to the concept of “home” in constitutional norms emphasizes the importance of this right and its unique context in each country. The definition of “home” is not limited to physical space only, but also reflects the values, priorities and philosophy of a society in protecting the personal freedoms and privacy of citizens.

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